

LUMI AI Factory

LUMI AI Factory Service Center

Empowering Europe's AI Ecosystem

D4.5

HPC API and documentation

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

The LUMI AI Factory Service Center is funded jointly by the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking under Grant Agreement 101234208 and the Participating States FI, CZ, DK, EE, NO, PL.

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Project Title	LUMI AI Factory Service Center
Project Acronym	LUMI-AIF
Project Number	101234208
Type of Action	HORIZON-JU-RIA
Topic	HORIZON-JU-EUROHPC-2025-AI-01-IBA-01
Starting Date of Project	01.03.2025
Ending Date of Project	29.02.2028
Duration of the Project	36 months
Website	lumi-ai-factory.eu

Work Package	WP ₄
Task	Task 4.4. Development of AI-ready computing environment and HPC API
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Version	1.0
Due Date	29.8.2025
Submission Date	27.8.2025

Dissemination level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	SEN: Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1.		Lukas Prediger	Draft for HPC-API User Stories
0.2.	26.6.2025	Juha Hulkkonen	Added MLOps content and some proposals
0.3.	2.7.2025	Juha Hulkkonen	Drafted the Introduction, restructured a bit and edited the other chapters
0.4	4.7.2025	Sebastian von Alfthan	Added first draft for FirecREST + Kubeflow
0.5	11.7.2025	Juha A. Lehtonen	Added first draft for FirecREST solution technical overview.
0.6	21.7.2025	Juha Hulkkonen	Re-write the Introduction, cleaning and refining other chapters.
0.7	25.7.2025	Juha Hulkkonen	Finalizing the draft
0.8	13.8.2025	Lukas Prediger	Changes to overall structure
0.9	21.8.2025	Pauliina Somerkoski	Resolved the changes and deleted comments. Small finishing touches.
1.0	27.8.2025	Anna Luoma	Final quality check performed by the PMO, sent to official review.

Glossary of Terms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
Airflow	Data-engineering oriented workflow engine
Aitta	AI Inference service created in CSC
API	Application Programming Interface
FirecREST	An open-source web API to access HPC resources. FirecREST is developed by Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS).
HEAppE	HEAppE Middleware (High-End Application Execution Middleware) is an open-source software framework to provides a interface to HPC resources. Developed at IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center.
HPC	High Performance Computing
Item	Description
Kubeflow	A popular workflow system for machine learning operations
LUMI-K	OpenShift based container cloud currently in development
LUMI-O	Ceph based object storage connected to LUMI system

ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations – The operation of machine learning systems using automated tools for training, testing, and deployment of machine learning models.
OpenID Connect	OpenID Connect (OIDC) is an identity layer built on top of OAuth 2.0 framework. It allows third party applications to verify the identity of the user based on authentication performed by an authorization server.
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface - a common form of a stateless web API using the HTTP protocol
S3	Simple Storage Service protocol to access object storage systems
Slurm	The Slurm Workload Manager is an open-source job scheduler for Linux based systems, used by many of the world's supercomputers and computer clusters.

Executive Summary

This document describes HPC-API development for LUMI AI Factory.

An HPC-API (High Performance Computing Application Programming Interface) is used to programmatically manage and interact with HPC environments. It functions for job management, like submitting and cancelling jobs on a supercomputer and querying their status, as well as handling data on the system.

The HPC-APIs deployed to LUMI are used by access various software components that are being developed for the LUMI AI Factory. Modern AI (Artificial Intelligence) development often relies on an extensive underlying software environment to support the machine learning workloads running in the system.

This document describes the deployment of a new HPC-API for LUMI. The aim is to set up an HPC-API that can be used with MLOps tools and containerized workflows to serve users of LUMI AI Factory in AI development tasks. The technology selected for this HPC-API is FirecREST developed by Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS).

This document also describes HEAppE as an alternative approach. HEAppE, developed by IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center (IT4I), is an open-source software framework that provides a secure and user-friendly interface to HPC resources. HEAppE is already used as part of some CSC services as well as isolated, dedicated HPC-API for some scientific projects.

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1. Introduction

Many commercial services in the field of AI are based on cloud platforms. Even though the latest containerised microservice solutions are capable and scalable, more parallel computing power is needed for the most demanding data pre-processing, AI training, finetuning and inference tasks.

The LUMI AI Factory consortium compute resources consist of access to LUMI and, later, LUMI-AI supercomputer as well as strong cloud platforms. Therefore, we are well positioned to empower cloud-based solutions with considerable HPC capacity. Combining these very different computing paradigms is not straightforward task. Programmatic access from cloud services to HPC is needed to combine these platforms. This Application Programming Interface (API) to be developed and delivered is referred as HPC-API in the following.

The HPC-API is an essential component to implement the LUMI AI Factory service portfolio as envisioned, of which an overview is presented in the following section. The HPC-API will allow us to connect to HPC capacity of LUMI and later LUMI-AI supercomputers from our cloud-based services. That connection and the emergent combination of those two computing platforms can enable novel ways to develop and offer AI services. Most of the LUMI AI Factory software environment components will require access to supercomputer resources.

There are existing technologies currently available to solve this issue, such as FirecREST and HEAppE which are described in more detail in Section 3. They have different approaches which are targeted to different use-cases and technologies. Key considerations for LUMI AI Factory are the convenience of usage, suitability to our needs, authentication and access key management. To select the right approach, requirements for the HPC-API are considered in Section 2, based on which a plan for the implementation of the HPC-API is presented in Section 4.

Typical uses cases are workflows supporting use of LLMs for text pre-processing, like dataset curation. Other considered use cases are LLM fine-tuning and LLM evaluation. The aim is to use the HPC-API to access these ready-made containerized workflows on the LUMI system. HPC-API extends the ways user can utilize the HPC resources from external tools or services on LUMI.

1.1 Introduction to LUMI AI Factory MLOps environment

LUMI AI Factory provides an MLOps environment designed around centrally operated core components and served applications, that are supported by a larger selection of recommended frameworks and complete MLOps stacks.

Planned core components for LUMI AI Factory MLOps environment are the open-source tools Kubeflow, to orchestrate the machine learning workflows, and MLflow, to track the training and to store the models and training metadata. Our self-developed Aitta AI inference service is complementing the offering and closing the MLOps loop visualized in the Figure 1, by providing the HPC-powered inference service even

for the heaviest generative models. Aitta is currently using a dedicated HEAppE instance for accessing the HPC.

Figure 1: MLOps Cycle to cover tools for continuous improvement and delivery of machine learning models

In the MLOps context the HPC-API will offer the essential avenue for Kubeflow to access LUMI resources to complement LUMI-K container cloud resources for more heavyweight use cases.

Kubeflow is a popular workflow system for machine learning operations, enjoying almost a de-facto standard status currently and providing smooth interoperability with commercial cloud environments. Kubeflow excels in orchestrating complex ML training and deployment pipelines, including pre-processing of data, performing training and running model inference. Kubeflow enables industry users who are used to cloud native tools on services offered by American hyperscalers an easy way to start using LUMI AI Factory services. A key target is to enable Kubeflow to run compute-heavy tasks on LUMI-G GPU nodes using the HPC-API, while light tasks can remain on LUMI-K.

MLflow is one of the core components extending the possibilities of Kubeflow for managing the machine learning lifecycle. It is already available for users on CSC's HPC systems to track ML training metrics locally. With the external MLflow application, a user can track the metrics outside of the HPC system for wider and longer-term usage. In the LUMI AI Factory MLOps toolkit, MLflow is offered as a stand-alone application on top of CSC container clouds, but also as integral part of Kubeflow to offer a seamless way

to track runs and version control the produced models. In addition to these specific functions, the standalone application opens all features of MLflow for the user.

The Aitta AI inference service is a general-purpose scalable service component to host AI models on a supercomputer. Aitta is offered for LUMI AI Factory users to run their AI models in a reliable and powerful computing system safely in Finland, while harnessing powers of energy efficient supercomputers. Aitta is currently under development and uses a dedicated instance of HEAppE deployed on CSC's cPouta cloud service to access HPC resources. Aitta is described in more detail in the Deliverable 4.3.

These components will be tightly integrated, making it easy to build fully automated and tracked workflows from data pre-processing to training, fine-tuning and evaluating and comparing models.

Other components planned to complement the core tools described above are Airflow, DVC and Grafana. The Airflow workflow engine supports wider, and especially more data engineering-oriented use cases compared to Kubeflow. Airflow is already in use in CSC's internal processes but not yet offered as a service for users. Data version control (DVC) is a popular tool for data versioning, complementing MLflow's machine learning model version controlling. For more complex workflows, Grafana provides excellent observability features to visualise and monitor every aspect of the data flow and processing. Grafana is already widely used at CSC for internal monitoring.

2. Requirements for HPC-API

A driving focus for the HPC-API is to serve LUMI AI Factory AI tool needs. The HPC-API should support MLOps tools like Kubeflow and Airflow to orchestrate various tasks on HPC systems in different steps of the ML lifecycle, as described above in Section 1.1.

However, the HPC-API should also be available outside the use of the MLOps environment and generally provide all users of the LUMI AI Factory with programmatic access to the HPC systems.

2.1 User stories for HPC-API usage

The following use cases have been identified to inform the requirements for an HPC-API. They are presented as a summary of typical use, followed by a concrete user story of a plausible fictional user and some requirements this poses towards the HPC-API.

2.1.1 User of LUMI AI Factory service offerings

Summary: A user is using a service provided by the LUMI AI Factory to execute HPC workloads/tasks on their own behalf and in a project, they have access to. The service uses the HPC-API transparently to the user.

User Story: Alice is a business user of the LUMI AI Factory. She has a user account on LUMI and is a member of a LUMI project that was granted computational resources. She wants to evaluate the suitability of different Large Language Models (LLMs) for a particular application using the MLOps services of the LUMI AI Factory. She prefers to work with high-level frameworks such as Kubeflow to deploy models quickly. She has some existing deployment scripts from a cloud provider she was using

previously and expects those to work ideally without changes. She does not want to handle low-level HPC-specific deployment details. She assumes a cloud-like architecture in which an LLM server running on LUMI can be accessed via HTTP from the other deployed services which drive her evaluation scripts and present inputs to the LLMs.

Current state on LUMI: Kubeflow is not currently available. It will be set it up on the coming LUMI-K Kubernetes cluster to support this kind of use cases (see Section 1.3).

Key takeaways: The HPC-API must be able to authenticate registered users and map workloads submitted by them to a project they are a member of, if sufficient computational resources are available. Crucially, it should be able to do so if access to the HPC-API originates from another LUMI AI Factory service, to which the user previously authenticated. The user can be authenticated every time they start a work session on the system/service. Furthermore, the HPC-API should enable integration of Kubeflow as well as enable routing of (HTTP) connections to processes deployed on the LUMI hardware.

2.1.2 User of LUMI AI Factory HPC-API

Summary: A user uses the HPC-API directly to programmatically launch HPC workloads/tasks from their own machine using custom scripts

User Story: Bob is a research user of the LUMI AI Factory. He has a user account with CSC and wants to evaluate the interplay of traditional HPC simulation and AI models. He uses his own custom-made scripts to track and organise his experiments. While his experiment workloads (simulation or AI training or inference runs) require to be run on an HPC system, his tracking scripts do not. He would like to run these locally and let them automatically deploy workloads (simulation or AI training or inference runs) on the LUMI hardware via an HPC-API.

Current state on LUMI: This is currently not directly supported.

Key takeaways: In addition to the takeaways from the previous section, the HPC-API must also offer a way to directly authenticate a user without that user first being mediated through another LUMI AI Factory service.

2.1.3 Client applications hosted by LUMI AI Factory projects

Summary: A user sets up a service that third-party users can access and which launches one (or several) previously configured workloads on behalf of the third-party user. The workload should be run in the context of the project of the user who set up the service but not use any individual user account.

User Story: Charlie is a researcher involved in a big EU research initiative that has been granted computing resources on LUMI. Part of the project is development of an LLM-based chat interface (chatbot) that online users can interrogate about the outcomes of simulations run in the scope of the project. Due to the size of the involved LLMs, Charlie needs to deploy this chat interface so that it runs the corresponding inference tasks on the LUMI-G hardware using the resources allocated to the research project. The actual web interface is hosted on a separate server (e.g. LUMI-K or CSC's Rahti/cPouta cloud service offerings). Since his users are not registered users of the LUMI AI Factory, he needs the HPC-API to authenticate the web server hosting the chatbot on a machine-to-machine basis, instead of being authenticated as an individual member of the research project.

Current state on LUMI: Several EU projects already fall into this usage category and typically deploy their own HPC-API instance (e.g., HEAppE). They are currently provisioned with so-called robot accounts, i.e., user accounts on the LUMI system that are not tied to an individual project member but have separate SSH credentials that are set up in the HPC-API instance configuration. These are set up manually by system administrators upon explicit request. Example projects: TerraDT, ClimateDT, DeployAI.

Key takeaways: The HPC-API must allow the registration of client applications for machine-to-machine authentication. Each client application must be uniquely mapped to a project. Ideally, credentials for client application have a long lifetime so that client application configuration does not need to be updated frequently.

Additional restrictions: The application/client deployed by the LUMI AI Factory user must not allow direct system access for third-party users but only run (one of) a set of predefined tasks that require use of the large-scale computational resources available on LUMI. Furthermore, it must be ensured that online users cannot extract the (machine-to-machine) credentials from the client.

3. Existing HPC-API software solutions

3.1 FirecREST HPC-API

3.1.1 Description of FirecREST

FirecREST is an open-source REST API for accessing HPC resources developed by the Swiss National Supercomputing Center (CSCS). The latest version is FirecREST v2, which is available at <https://github.com/eth-cscs/firecrest-v2>. The API provides a standardized interface to access HPC infrastructures, with authentication and authorization, supporting multiple schedulers, storages, and filesystems types. FirecREST provides endpoints for

- **Status:** system information and availability
- **Filesystem:** file management and transfers
- **Compute:** job management

It implements a standard OpenID Connect authorization that enables users to access the system with their normal user account. This enables it to support the first two user stories (2.1.1, 2.1.2), and is a key reason for why it is being deployed in the LUMI AI Factory.

3.1.2 Architecture

Figure 2: FirecREST architecture

3.1.3 Features

FirecREST is high-performance proxy for accessing HPC resources, such as workload schedulers or storage systems. FirecREST provides:

- Standardized RESTful API interface
- Authentication and authorization layer based on OpenID Connect
- Access to HPC resources using personal account
- Execution of user-defined compute, filesystem and storage operations
- High-performance asynchronous SSH connection pooling
- Support for Slurm and OpenPBS schedulers
- Support for Slurmrestd API interaction over an SSH connection

- Support for DeIC SSH Certificate Authority service
- Support for asynchronous large file transfers
- Modular, lightweight software architecture
- Publicly available integration libraries and examples for popular tools, such as Apache Airflow

3.1.4 Authentication and authorization

FirecREST implements standard OpenID Connect authorization for REST API access. A user sends their OAuth access token, issued by a trusted identity provider, in the authorization header for every request sent to FirecREST API. FirecREST performs offline token validation against a predetermined list of trusted issuers and their public signing keys (JWKs). The connection between FirecREST and HPC cluster is established using an SSH connection as the user authenticating to FirecREST API.

The SSH service on the HPC cluster is configured to authorize user logins based on SSH certificates issued by a central certificate authority (SSH CA). SSH CA is a service that can exchange a valid OAuth access token from a trusted issuer for an SSH certificate for the subject the access token is associated with. This allows automated generation of short-lived SSH access credentials for identities verified by the identity provider. FirecREST uses this mechanism for creating temporary SSH credentials for accessing the target HPC cluster on the user's behalf.

FirecREST does not persist any data related to SSH certificates. An ed25519 key-pair generated on-the-fly, on-demand, is used as the basis for retrieving a certificate from SSH CA service. The key-pair and certificate are discarded immediately after an SSH connection has been established, or in case of a connection failure, after the first connection attempt. An established SSH connection is kept open in a user-specific server-side connection pool entry for a predetermined duration of time, to serve subsequent API requests. When the connection pool entry has reached its idle timeout or maximum lifetime, a new connection is automatically established upon demand, using the same procedure.

3.1.5 Use case support

FirecREST can be used in a variety of different ways for abstracting interaction with HPC workload managers and file system operations. It supports all three user stories in 2.1, but we aim to in particular enable the first two user stories:

- 2.1.1
- 2.1.2

User of LUMI AI Factory service offerings: FirecREST API can be used to provide seamless access to user's HPC resources by incorporating it as a backend for an interactive web application, visualized in Figure 3. A web application will implement browser-based user authorization and token retrieval using the standard OpenID Connect Authorization Code Flow. FirecREST is configured to trust tokens issued by the identity provider used by the web application. This allows the web application to establish a connection to the FirecREST backend on behalf of the user, using the access token issued by the identity provider. Using the access token, FirecREST can establish a connection to the target HPC cluster, to perform tasks requested by the user.

Figure 3: Backend for an interactive web application

User of LUMI AI Factory HPC-API: FirecREST API can be used as an alternative for an SSH connection with command-line or desktop tools, by implementing FirecREST connection using authentication using OpenID Connect Device Authorization Flow, visualized in Figure 4. This allows interacting with HPC resources using personal user account, from systems with no web browser or limited input capability (e.g. CI/CD workflows), or from non-browser-based desktop or command line applications, while retaining security benefits of a regular login flow, such as support for multi-factor authentication.

With Device Authorization Flow, an authorization request towards the identity provider is initiated by a non-browser application and will present the unique device authorization code it received to the user. User can then use web browser on another device to log in to the identity provider web UI using their personal credentials and insert the device authorization code. This permits the requesting application to retrieve an access token on their behalf, which allows the application to connect to FirecREST API as the user who authorized it.

Figure 4: Standalone API for CLI or desktop tools

3.2 HEAppE Middleware

3.2.1 Motivation

HEAppE Middleware (High-End Application Execution Middleware) is an open-source software framework that provides a secure and user-friendly interface to HPC resources. Designed with modularity, multi-user support, and REST API accessibility, HEAppE enables seamless integration of HPC infrastructure with custom user applications, web portals, and third-party services. Developed in-house at IT4Innovations National Supercomputing Center, HEAppE is an implementation of the HPC-as-a-Service concept.

HPC-as-a-Service is a well-known term in high-performance computing. It enables users to access an HPC infrastructure without a need to buy and manage their own physical servers or data center infrastructure. Through this service, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) can take advantage of the technology without an upfront investment in the hardware. This approach further lowers the entry barrier for users and SMEs who are interested in utilizing massive parallel computers but often do not have the necessary level of expertise in this area.

HEAppE manages and provides information about submitted and running jobs and their data between the client application and the HPC infrastructure. HEAppE is able to submit required computation or simulation on HPC infrastructure, monitor the progress and notify the user should the need arise. It provides necessary functions for job management, monitoring and reporting, user authentication and authorization, file transfer, encryption, and various notification mechanisms.

3.2.2 Architecture

HEAppE Middleware follows a modular architecture (Figure 5). The system consists of several key components. At its core, the HEAppE application includes modules for API handling, service orchestration, business logic, data access, file transfer, and HPC connection management. The API module provides REST API endpoints that allow external systems and client applications to interact with HEAppE. The service module coordinates internal operations, while the business logic module implements core functionalities such as job and data management. Secure and efficient interaction with HPC systems is facilitated by the HPC connection module, which manages SSH-based access to remote job schedulers such as PBS and SLURM. To protect sensitive information such as SSH keys and credentials for the access to the HPC, the system incorporates a dedicated secure vault module.

Figure 5: HEAppE architecture

3.2.3 Features and Security

HEAppE Middleware provides:

- Seamless HPC access via a standardized REST API

- Templated jobscripsts enabling easy HPC application execution and monitoring without direct access to the cluster
- REST API for SLURM or PBS batch job management
- Support for other batch schedulers or metaschedulers through plugin interface
- Secure credential management for HPC data transfer
- Audited remote user-to-HPC access
- Secure vault for HPC access credentials
- Authentication via Personalized or Robot accounts with Shared or Exclusive access modes
- Protection against brute-force attacks, rate limiting, and minimized data exposure
- OpenID token role-based authentication

HEAppE implements several key security features to ensure secure access to HPC resources.

From the authentication point of view HEAppE supports two access modes. First one uses personalized user accounts i.e. one-to-one mapping of user credentials meaning that the HPC compute job executed via HEAppE will be submitted under an actual HPC user account. Second approach utilizes so-called robot accounts where the API users don't have direct access to an HPC infrastructure but HEAppE maps each compute job execution to a selected robot account, thus allowing controlled and restrictive access to the HPC resources. These robot accounts are created for a concrete resource allocation on a specific HPC infrastructure.

To prevent arbitrary command execution, users can only run predefined job execution templates called Command Templates. Each template defines a script or executable binary, that will be executed on an HPC infrastructure together with any dependencies or third-party software it might require.

3.2.4 Future work and References

HEAppE Middleware is an open-source software with GPL v3 license. It is under constant development with the aim of having quarterly releases containing bug fixes and newly supported features based on feedback from the users and related projects' requirements.

HEAppE landing page <https://heappe.eu>

HEAppE source codes <https://github.com/It4innovations/HEAppE>

HEAppE documentation <https://heappe.it4i.cz/docs>

4. Design of the LUMI AI Factory HPC-API

4.1 Selection of solution components

As described in section 3.1.5, FirecREST supports the two first use cases, which are of key importance. In the first use case, the LUMI AI Factory can provide MLOps web services where users access LUMI resources under their own identity. In the second use case, users can configure single-user access on their own laptops and use LUMI as an extension of their local workflows and tools. Both of these can be

supported by a single centralized API service. In principle the third use case could be covered using robot accounts, but initially this usage may not be supported.

HEAppE was originally designed to meet the third use case. In that case API users don't have direct access to an HPC infrastructure but HEAppE gives controlled and restrictive access to the HPC resources via robot accounts. Projects can also independently set up HEAppE and tune it for their needs. No centralized installation is being planned for LUMI.

4.2 Implementation plan

4.2.1 Integrating FirecREST with LUMI and CSC infrastructure

FirecREST API will be integrated with CSC authentication proxy user-auth. This supports OpenID Connect and the required authorization flows. Another key service is an SSH-CA service. This provides the actual SSH certificate that FirecREST uses to access the supercomputer on behalf of the user. IN 2025, CSC is setting up a SSH-CA service based on the DeIC SSH Certificate Authority Library (<https://github.com/wayf-dk/sshca>). FirecREST recently received support for this solution.

4.2.2 Kubeflow HPC offloading via FirecREST

Kubeflow is a Kubernetes-based MLOps platform that provides a user-friendly way to handle the full life cycle of an ML model, enabling users to develop, orchestrate, and deploy machine learning workflows. As described in Section 1.1, it is a key component of the LUMI AI Factory MLOps environment.

LUMI AI Factory Service Center will operate a Kubeflow service on the upcoming LUMI-K container cloud platform. This platform offers a managed, multi-tenant Kubernetes based service running on CPU compute nodes of LUMI. It has no direct access to Slurm or the Lustre file system but will need to access the LUMI HPC partitions via the FirecREST REST API and LUMI-O object store system via the Simple Storage Service (S3) protocol. Users will authenticate using OpenID Connect, enabling seamless single sign-on across the platform. The authentication system will automatically provision access tokens for both FirecREST and LUMI-O services.

A key target is to enable Kubeflow to run compute heavy tasks on LUMI-G GPU nodes using this API (HPC offload), while light tasks can remain on LUMI-K. The main use cases that will be offloaded are:

- **ML workflows:** Kubeflow Pipelines are complex ML workflows that can be expressed as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) of tasks. Each task is typically a container that runs in Kubernetes, doing e.g. data pre-processing, training, evaluation, etc. The primary goal is to enable these tasks to be offloaded.
- **Hyperparameter tuning:** The Katib component can be used for hyperparameter tuning by launching many training jobs in parallel. A potential future goal is to offload these to HPC.

Some use cases for Kubeflow will not be offloaded to HPC:

- **Interactive Jupyter notebooks:** Typically used for data analysis and model development tasks. The LUMI supercomputer already provides a web interface where Jupyter notebooks can be run on, hence we will in this work not implement HPC offloading for this component. Some data processing and model development can still be done also on the LUMI-K nodes.

- **Serving models:** The KServe component is an inference service component for serving the developed models. In the LUMI AI Factory MLOps environment the Aitta service is the main model serving platform; hence no integration of KServe is currently planned.

4.2.2.1 Implementation plan

The goal is to keep the pipeline definition and user experience as close to normal as possible. The most straightforward approach is to implement a custom Kubernetes pipeline component. This allows the user to define the container image and commands to be run, a set of input data (e.g. S3 path), a S3 path where output data is to be placed, and finally a specification of the HPC resources required for the computation (number of GPUs, max job time, accounting project, etc.). When the component is launched as part of a Kubeflow pipeline, it runs as a lightweight pod in LUMI-K. This pod does not perform the actual computation but instead launches and monitors a job on the HPC system to do so. It also transfers data to and from the HPC system. All these tasks can be performed using FirecREST REST API calls.

In addition to a generic component, it is also possible to develop more specialized components for specific tasks such as training, making the components easier to use.

An important consideration is that the LUMI HPC partitions are only able to run Apptainer or Singularity containers. This is not a major problem since they can transparently convert Docker containers into their specific formats when running. A key task is still to provide a good set of containers that can be used for parallel large-scale tasks on the HPC system, that are able to efficiently utilize GPUs across multiple nodes and MPI. The work to develop this set of containers is described in Deliverable 4.4. in detail.

4.2.2.2 Alternative approaches and future work

It should be possible to use a similar approach as the Kubeflow pipelines in Katib, Kubeflows hyperparameter tuning framework, where FirecREST is used to offload trial jobs to HPC.

An interesting alternative to the pipeline component approach mentioned above is to implement a generic custom resource (CRD) representing FirecREST. Such a FirecRESTJob CRD would function like existing job types (TFJob, PyTorchJob) in Kubeflow. Technically, this also requires implementation of a controller that watches FirecRESTJob resources, translates specifications to FirecREST API calls, manages job lifecycle, and reports status information back to the Kubernetes API. The benefits of the CRD implementation are that it enables us to implement the FirecREST integration once instead of duplicating that logic across several pipeline components. Pipeline components then become thin wrappers that create FirecRESTJob resources and wait for completion. Another main benefit is that they would integrate much better into Kubernetes, and normal tooling can be used for monitoring and management. However, as this is likely a more complex task than adding a generic pipeline component, the latter option will be explored first, and investigate implementation of a CRD in later stages of the project.